

23 **Abstract**

24 A hybrid material (nano-metal organic framework@organic polymer, named as nano-
25 MOF@polymer) was applied for the first time as sorbent for on-line solid-phase
26 extraction capillary electrophoresis with ultraviolet detection (SPE-CE-UV). The
27 resulting material was prepared building layer-by-layer a HKUST-1 (Hong Kong
28 University of Science and Technology-1) nano-MOF onto the polymer surface, which
29 allowed controlling the thickness and maximizing the active surface area. The sorbent
30 was widely characterized at micro- and nano-scale to validate the synthesis and to
31 establish the material properties. Then, fritless microcartridges (2 mm) were assembled
32 by packing only a few micrograms of sorbent particles and investigated for
33 preconcentration of fluoroquinolones (FQs) in several real samples (river water, human
34 urine and whole cow milk). Under the optimized conditions, the sample (*ca.* 60 μL) was
35 loaded in separation background electrolyte (BGE, 50 mM phosphate (pH 7)), and
36 retained analytes were eluted using a small volume of 2% v/v formic acid in methanol
37 (*ca.* 50 nL). The SPE-CE-UV method was validated in terms of linearity, limit of
38 detection (LOD), limit of quantification (LOQ), repeatability, reproducibility and
39 reusability. The developed method showed a LOD decreasing until 1 ng L⁻¹ when larger
40 volumes of sample were loaded (*ca.* 180 μL), which was 500,000 times lower than by
41 CE-UV. This undescribed sensitivity enhancement would arise from the homogenous and
42 populated MOF nano-domains and the appropriate permeability of the hybrid material,
43 which would promote high extraction efficiency and loading capacity. Furthermore, the
44 sorbent showed appropriate selectivity regardless the analyzed complex environmental,
45 biological or food matrix samples, achieving excellent detectability and recoveries (>
46 90%).

47 **Keywords:** capillary electrophoresis, fluoroquinolones, hybrid composite, metal organic
48 framework, on-line solid-phase extraction, microscale

49 **1. Introduction**

50 Metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) are coordination polymers built from suitable organic
51 ligands and metal ions that form ordered porous networks [1]. They present several
52 fascinating properties for analytical chemistry [2] and other research fields such as large
53 surface area, chemical stability, tunable chemistry, etc., which have been demonstrated
54 over the years [3,4].

55 Nowadays, nanoscale materials are of great interest for a large variety of applications
56 [5,6]. New or improved features appear when material size is reduced. In particular,
57 regarding nano-MOFs, an enlarged surface area and superior mass transference (due to
58 the short transport routes) lead to a major accessibility of the active sites for the target
59 analytes [7,8].

60 Several approaches can be followed to decrease and control the particle size of MOFs,
61 such as assisting the synthesis with ultrasound [7,9] or introducing modulators in the
62 precursor mixtures [10,11]. Alternatively, the layer-by-layer assembly [12–14] allows
63 controlling not only the particle size, but also maximizing the active surface area for
64 analyte interaction [15]. In addition, the MOF layers can be built up in a polymeric
65 organic support to obtain a hybrid composite [12,16] with superior features than the
66 individual components. As unique advantage, the layer-by-layer approach does not
67 require high temperature/pressure neither toxic solvents (e.g. solvothermal or reflux) [17],
68 and preparation times can be shorter if the number of synthetic cycles are restrained.

69 To date, the potential of nano-MOF composites has been explored in gas storage [18], as
70 carrier platform [19], sensing [20], catalysis [21] and separation [22], among other fields.
71 Meanwhile, the investigation of nano-MOFs in sample treatment is still in its first steps,
72 especially at the microscale application [2]. Several challenges remain in the design of
73 nano-MOF based composites as sorbents for the efficient sample clean-up and

74 preconcentration when dealing with samples of limited volume and miniaturized
75 techniques [16]. In this regard, on-line solid-phase extraction capillary electrophoresis
76 (SPE-CE), which requires minute amounts of such sorbents, is an excellent candidate to
77 demonstrate and expand the applicability in microextraction of nano-MOFs and their
78 hybrid polymeric composites [23–29].

79 In SPE-CE [25–29], a microcartridge containing an appropriate sorbent is connected near
80 the inlet of the separation capillary. The microextraction device allows loading a larger
81 volume of sample than in conventional CE (hundreds of μL vs tens of nL), retaining the
82 analytes of interest and cleaning-up the sample matrix interferences. The analyte
83 preconcentration is achieved after injecting a small volume of eluent (tens of nL) before
84 applying the voltage for the separation and detection. Nowadays, SPE-CE is widely
85 recognized as an efficient and versatile strategy to enhance sensitivity of CE, obtaining
86 typical preconcentration factors from 100 to 10,000 [25]. A broad range of sorbents with
87 different selectivity have been applied to analyze a great variety of analytes, from
88 commercial chromatographic particle sorbents [25] (C8, C18, HLB, cationic or anionic
89 exchange, etc.) to less conventional particle sorbents based on immunoaffinity [26],
90 silicon carbide [27], aptamer affinity [28] and polymeric monoliths with gold
91 nanoparticles [29]. In all cases, as with many other extraction techniques at the microscale
92 that require a minute amount of sorbent, SPE-CE struggles with the necessity of
93 improving extraction efficiency and loading capacity, while decreasing non-specific
94 retention. In addition, in SPE-CE is also crucial to make compatible the sorbent
95 physicochemical characteristics and retention/elution mechanisms with the on-line
96 electrophoretic separation and detection. Therefore, the development of novel high-
97 performance sorbents to further expand the applicability of microextraction techniques,
98 including SPE-CE, is a major concern.

99 In this study, a hybrid composite made up of a nano-MOF (HKUST-1, Hong Kong
100 University of Science and Technology-1) and an organic polymer (synthesized with
101 methacrylic acid (MAA) as monomer) was prepared, characterized and applied as sorbent
102 in SPE-CE with ultraviolet detection (SPE-CE-UV). The method was optimized and
103 validated with standards and then applied to river water, human urine and whole cow milk
104 samples. The nano-MOF was built onto the monolithic polymer using the layer-by-layer
105 approach. The resulting material was extensively characterized at micro- and nano-scale,
106 before investigating its applicability for the trace analysis of drugs in complex samples.
107 Fluoroquinolones (FQs), which are a widely used group of broad-spectrum antibiotics in
108 human and veterinary medicine, were selected as target compounds. Due to their
109 extensive use, they have a great interest in pharmaceutical, environmental and food
110 analysis. As far as we know, this is the first study reporting a nano-MOF@polymer
111 composite as sorbent for SPE-CE.

112

113 **2. Experimental section**

114 Reagents, materials, sample collection, instruments and apparatus are included in the
115 electronic supplementary information.

116

117 **2.1. Synthesis of organic polymer**

118 The porous polymer monolith was prepared according to a previous study with minor
119 changes [12]. Briefly, the functional monomer and the cross-linker were MAA (liquid,
120 0.0435 g) and EDMA (liquid, 0.4628 g), respectively. Porogenic solvents were DMSO
121 (liquid, 1.5005 g) and PEG-6000 (solid, 0.4981 g). A pre-polymerization mixture was
122 weighed in a glass vial and heated (60 °C) to dissolve the PEG. Then, after reaching room
123 temperature, the initiator AIBN (0.0049 g) was added and homogenized using a vortex,

124 sonicated for 15 min in an ice bath (to avoid heat up during sonication), and purged with
125 a nitrogen stream for 10 min before carrying the polymerization in an oven (60 °C)
126 overnight. After this time, the monolith was cooled at room temperature and the bulk
127 material was milled with a ceramic mortar. The powder was washed with MeOH several
128 times to remove unreacted reagents and dried under vacuum. Finally, it was sieved and
129 particles ranging in size from 100 to 200 μm were selected for nano-MOF layer-by-layer
130 preparation.

131

132 **2.2. Growth of HKUST-1 onto polymer surface**

133 Layer-by-layer assembly was the approach selected to build the hybrid composite [12].
134 Concisely, two solutions were prepared: solution a) containing 10 mmol (199.2 mg) of
135 $\text{Cu}(\text{AcO})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 100 mL of EtOH; and solution b) containing 10 mmol (209.5 mg) of
136 H_3BTC in 100 mL of EtOH. Both were sonicated until homogenization. After that, 250
137 mg of organic polymer powder was weighed in a polypropylene tube and 10 mL of
138 solution a) was added and magnetically stirred for 15 min. After washing with EtOH, 10
139 mL of solution b) was dropwise added under magnetic stirring and then the stirring was
140 kept for 30 more minutes. Then, the material was washed again with EtOH to complete a
141 MOF layer. The synthesis was finished after completing 4 cycles, as in our previous study
142 [12]. The resultant blue powder was collected by vacuum filtration (nylon filter, 0.22 μm
143 pore diameter) and gently rinsed with MeOH. The composite was air dried under vacuum
144 at room temperature and sieved to save particles with size higher than 200 μm .
145 The material synthesis was thoroughly monitored by measuring the absorbance of the
146 supernatant of solutions a) and b) before and after each impregnation step at the
147 absorption maxima of both reagents (800 nm for $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ acetate and 252 nm for organic
148 linker).

149

150 **2.3. CE**

151 CE-UV experiments were done at 25 °C in a 57 cm total length (L_T) (48.5 cm effective
152 length, L_D) \times 75 μ m internal diameter (i.d.) \times 375 μ m outer diameter (o.d.) capillary. New
153 capillaries were activated flushing at 930 mbar with H₂O (15 min), 1 M NaOH (15 min)
154 and H₂O (15 min). Between analyses, the same sequence of solutions was used for
155 conditioning but reducing the step durations to 2 min. Between days, capillaries were
156 regenerated flushing with 1 M HCl (15 min) followed by the activation sequence.
157 Samples were injected at 50 mbar for 3 s (*ca.* 35 nL, calculated with the Hagen-Poiseuille
158 equation [30]). The separation voltage was +20 kV (cathode in the outlet end, normal
159 polarity) and the detection wavelength was 280 nm. If necessary, capillaries were stored
160 for short periods of time (1-5 days) after flushing with water for 2 min. For long-term
161 storage, the capillaries were dried with air.

162 The optimized BGE was a 50 mM phosphate buffer solution at pH 7. It was prepared
163 daily weighing Na₂HPO₄ (397 mg) and NaH₂PO₄ (303 mg) in a polypropylene tube. Next,
164 80 mL of water was added and properly mixed. Then, the pH was adjusted to 7 using 0.1
165 M NaOH. Finally, the solution volume was made up to 100 mL in a volumetric flask. The
166 BGE was degassed for 15 min by sonication before its use. The 2 M phosphate buffer
167 solution for sample preparation was prepared following the above-mentioned protocol
168 with minor modifications.

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170

171

172 **2.4. SPE-CE**

173 Figure S1 shows a picture of a SPE-CE capillary installed in the cartridge cassette with
174 the microcartridge inserted near the inlet end, and some magnifications under the
175 microscope. Fritless particle-packed microcartridges were prepared as described
176 elsewhere with some modifications [25]. In order to avoid excessive backpressure,
177 capillary blockage and electric current failure during SPE-CE experiments, it was
178 necessary to pack the microcartridges with a very small amount (2 mm length, *ca* 100 μg)
179 of 200-250 μm nano-MOF@polymer particles. The use of sorbent particles with a size
180 larger than the inner diameter of the separation capillary (75 μm) made unnecessary frits
181 to avoid particle leaking during the operation. The microcartridge body (4 mm $L_T \times 250$
182 μm i.d. \times 375 μm o.d.) was half-full filled by vacuum with the sorbent particles, while
183 the inlet fragment of the separation capillary (8.3 cm $L_T \times 75 \mu\text{m}$ i.d. \times 375 μm o.d.) was
184 connected to one of the ends with a plastic sleeve. Then, the SPE-CE capillary was
185 extended to full length connecting to the other end the outlet fragment of the separation
186 capillary (48.3 cm $L_T \times 75 \mu\text{m}$ i.d. \times 375 μm o.d.). In order to ensure mechanical
187 resistance and to extend the operation even flushing at 2 bar, the microcartridge was
188 sealed forming a capsule with a bi-component epoxy-resin glue (Figure S1A).

189 Under the optimized conditions, SPE-CE capillaries were conditioned by flushing at 930
190 mbar with H_2O (5 min), MeOH (10 min) and BGE (5 min), followed by application of
191 20 kV voltage and a final flush with water (15 min). After this packing conditioning step,
192 the volume collected by flushing water at 930 mbar for 10 min was *ca.* 60 μL . The
193 capillary was discarded if collected volumes were significantly different than this value.

194 Standard and sample solutions were loaded at 930 mbar for 10 min. Then, the capillary
195 was washed by flushing with BGE for 60 s to eliminate interferences and fill the capillary
196 before the separation. The retained analytes were eluted at 100 mbar for 5 s with a small
197 volume (*ca.* 50 nL) of 2% FA (formic acid) v/v in MeOH. The plug of eluent was pushed

198 from the inlet with BGE at 100 mbar for 60 s to improve repeatability between analyses
199 and to avoid current disruption or failure. Finally, +20 kV were applied for the
200 electrophoretic separation at 25 °C. To avoid carry over between consecutive analyses,
201 the capillary was flushed with MeOH (90 s) and H₂O (60 s).

202 **2.5. Quality parameters**

203 The quality parameters for SPE-CE were determined with standard mixtures as follows:
204 linearity was investigated at concentrations ranging from 0.1 to 80 µg L⁻¹; repeatability
205 (intra-day, single microcartridge and n=5) and reproducibility (inter-day, 3 days, single
206 microcartridge/day and n=5) were evaluated at 1 µg L⁻¹ as the relative standard deviation
207 (% , RSD) of peak areas. The LOD and limit of quantification (LOQ) were determined
208 from the most diluted analyzed mixture when S/N values were 3 or 10, respectively. The
209 reusability was evaluated by consecutive analyses at 1 µg L⁻¹. The microcartridge was
210 discarded when the peak areas decreased more than 20% compared to the mean value of
211 the first three analyses with the microcartridge under consideration.

212

213 **2.6. Sample analysis**

214 The samples of river water and urine were firstly tempered and an appropriate volume of
215 2 M phosphate solution was added to obtain a final concentration of 50 mM phosphate in
216 the loading samples. Then, pH was adjusted to 7 with 0.1 M NaOH. The mixtures were
217 shaken and left 30 min in the darkness. After this period, they were centrifuged for 15 min
218 at 4,500 g and vacuum filtered (nylon filter, 0.22 µm pore size) to remove suspended
219 matter. For urine sample, a 1/10 dilution was made before the SPE-CE analysis due to the
220 complexity of the matrix. Fortified samples (1 µg L⁻¹) were prepared by spiking the river
221 water and urine samples before the sample preparation with appropriate volumes of FQ
222 standard mixture (100 mg L⁻¹).

223 In the case of whole cow milk, the samples were tempered and protein precipitation was
224 accomplished by mixing cold MeCN (stored at -20 °C) with milk samples at a 6:1 ratio
225 (v/v). Then, the mixture was vortexed for 90 s and kept in the freezer for 1 h to ensure the
226 maximum protein precipitation. After that, the suspension was centrifuged for 15 min at
227 4,500 g. The supernatant was collected and the remaining pellet was rinsed twice with
228 cold MeCN (*ca.* 1/10 of the ACN volume used in the precipitation step). After agitation
229 and centrifugation, supernatants were pooled and evaporated to dryness using miVAC
230 sample concentrator (centrifugation at 25 °C under vacuum). Finally, the samples were
231 reconstituted to the original volume with BGE and the pH was readjusted to 7 with 0.1 M
232 HCl before SPE-CE analysis. Fortified milk samples (1 µg L⁻¹) were prepared as for river
233 water and urine samples.

234

235 **3. Results and discussion**

236 **3.1. Choice of material**

237 The selection of the right material in SPE is critical since it will strongly influence
238 recoveries, and subsequently, method performance. The nano-MOF@polymer composite
239 was designed taking advantage of the monolithic features (good permeability, cheap and
240 simple synthesis) [29,31,32] and the MOF characteristics (great surface area, selectivity,
241 high surface-to-volume ratio, among others) [2,13]. Thanks to that, the resulting sorbent
242 will overcome typical problems encountered with other sorbents such as limited
243 recoveries, inappropriate particle size, heterogeneity, losses of material or high
244 backpressures [16,33]. The composite was prepared using the layer-by-layer approach
245 since it allows a reproducible synthesis controlling the thickness and maximizing the
246 active surface area [34,35]. A MAA based monolith was selected since it presents a great
247 number of carboxylic residues for Cu(II) coordination. The specific choice of HKUST-1

248 against the existing wide MOF catalogue was done due to (see Table S1 and Figure S2):
249 i) non-toxicity and availability of copper as metal centre and well-known trimesic acid
250 chemistry as bridging organic ligand [36]; ii) suitable pore size [37] (9 Å) allowing the
251 entrance and interaction of target FQs; iii) wide range of potential interaction forces
252 between sorbent and analytes such as hydrogen bonding (with amino, ketone or
253 carboxylic groups), hydrophobic effects and π -interaction (between aromatic rings) and
254 electrostatic interactions depending on pH (between surface composite charge and
255 ionized groups from FQs). Bearing in mind all these considerations, the HKUST-
256 1@polymer was evaluated as sorbent for microextraction in SPE-CE.

257

258 **3.2. Characterization of the HKUST-1@polymer composite**

259 An extensive characterization of the resulting composite was done in order to validate the
260 synthesis and study its morphological, structural and chemical features.

261 Several techniques were applied for monitoring the correct formation of HKUST-1 onto
262 the monolithic surface. As can be seen in the XRD patterns shown in Figure 1A, the
263 typical peaks from the HKUST-1 simulated pattern appear at the final hybrid composite
264 (from 10 to 30 °). Furthermore, at around 10° an intense signal corresponding to organic
265 monolith can be observed, which suggests a higher proportion of polymer compared to
266 HKUST-1. Figure 1B shows the FT-IR spectra over the range of 500–4000 cm⁻¹. As it
267 can be observed, the characteristic peaks of HKUST-1 are present in the final composite
268 (1600, 1550, 1375 and 750 cm⁻¹), but with lower intensities due to the smaller amount of
269 MOF on the surface compared to polymeric network. Absorption of alkyl C-H stretch at
270 2900 cm⁻¹ and carbonyl C=O stretch at 1750 cm⁻¹ are originated from the methacrylate
271 based polymer (for comparison of the composite and the bare monolith spectra, see Figure
272 1B). At the same time aromatic C=C bending is recognizable as a small band at 1600 cm⁻¹

273 ¹. In HKUST-1, C=O symmetric and asymmetric modes are present centered at 1625 cm⁻¹
274 ¹ jointly with C=C aromatic bending. Both modes are clearly shown in the composite
275 spectrum. FT-IR spectra from MOF precursors were also measured (Figure S3) in order
276 to verify the HKUST-1 formation. Comparing the organic ligand and HKUST-1 spectra,
277 vibrational mode of -OH from carboxylic acids at 2500-3000 cm⁻¹ disappears, which
278 indicates the coordination between carboxylic acid and copper (II). Furthermore, in
279 HKUST-1, bands of (C-O) and (C=O) are shifted to *ca.* 1375 and 1600 cm⁻¹, while in
280 trimesic acid spectrum are originally placed at 1250 and 1700 cm⁻¹, respectively. This
281 fact further confirmed the Cu(II) coordination.

282 Morphological exploration was carried out by electron microscopy. In the HRTEM
283 micrograph of Figure 1C can be seen the homogeneous distribution of the HKUST-1
284 particles on the monolith surface. The particle size was ranging from 7 to 9 nm (n=25),
285 which confirmed the nanosize of MOF crystals. The SEM image of Figure 1D reveals
286 significant morphological differences compared to the typical globular shape of an
287 organic monolith [12,38]. Clusters with spherical particles are depicted, with a rough
288 surface due to the aggregation of HKUST-1 nano-domains (*ca.* size 45-55 nm).

289 Information from both electronic microscopies agrees with the hypothesis of homogenous
290 decoration on the surface due to the layer-by-layer strategy. The imaging analysis was
291 continued with STEM-HAADF micrographs (Figure S4A) at 1.2·10⁶X of magnification.
292 In the sub-nano field, an average particle size of 4 nm (n=25) is observed for the HKUST-
293 1 crystals in the HKUST-1@polymer. Furthermore, well-dispersed copper and,
294 consequently MOF, is detected by EDX elemental mapping analysis as illustrated in a
295 small area in Figure S4B. The EDX spectra also indicates a *ca.* 9% (m/m) of copper
296 attached to the surface of the polymer. This detailed characterization was completed with
297 the information from the N₂ adsorption isotherms obtained in a previous study [12]. N₂

298 isotherms clearly showed two adsorption steps from microporous (at low relative
299 pressure) and macroporous (high relative pressure) behaviors due to MOF and monolithic
300 natures, respectively. The surface area estimated with the BJH model for HKUST-
301 1@polymer was $170 \text{ m}^2\text{g}^{-1}$ vs $9 \text{ m}^2\text{g}^{-1}$ for the bare monolith. All these facts support the
302 idea of a large active surface area of the hybrid composite, with a homogeneous
303 distribution of the nano-MOF crystals throughout the polymer surface, ready to be
304 accessible by the target analytes when applied as sorbent for microextraction in SPE-CE.
305

306 **3.3. Development of the HKUST-1@polymer-SPE-CE-UV method**

307 In order to achieve the highest analyte recoveries and detection sensitivity, several
308 parameters affecting the method performance needed to be optimized using FQ standard
309 mixtures. Since HKUST-1 was supposed to present limited stability if subjected to acidic
310 pH for a long time, a neutral BGE was selected for the separation to ensure an extended
311 lifetime. After some preliminary experiments by CE to check that an appropriate
312 separation could be obtained for DAN, EFX and DFX with a 50 mM phosphate buffer at
313 pH 7, the starting SPE-CE experiments were performed loading a $20 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ standard
314 mixture in water for 5 min at 930 mbar followed by washing with BGE for 60 s at
315 930 mbar. One of the most important steps in a SPE procedure is the elution, which should
316 be quantitative using the smallest volume of solvent to ensure high enrichment factors.
317 The composition of the eluent was optimized injecting a volume of 10 s at 100 mbar. In
318 all experiments, the plug of eluent was pushed from the inlet with BGE at 100 mbar for
319 60 s to improve repeatability between analyses and to avoid current disruption or failure.
320 First, the MeOH content in the eluent was kept constant (90%, v/v) and H₂O:FA
321 proportion was varied from 1 to 5% (v/v) of FA. The largest peak areas were obtained
322 with 2% (v/v) of FA. A lower acid content led to a peak area diminution, and no FQs

323 were detected without adding acid. In contrast higher acid contents did not produce a peak
324 area increase but significant peak distortions. Using a 2% (v/v) of FA, the percentage of
325 organic solvent in the eluent was studied for 80, 90 and 98% v/v of MeOH. As can be
326 observed in Figure 2A, the largest peak areas were observed with a 98% (v/v) of MeOH.
327 Different experiments were performed to improve these results using MeCN and/or HAc.
328 However, low repeatability, peak distortion and current breakdowns were observed.
329 Therefore, a 2% (v/v) of FA in MeOH was selected as the optimized eluent. Regarding
330 the elution solvent volume, a study varying the injection time from 5 to 15 s at 100 mbar
331 was performed. Volumes injected greater than 10s (*ca.* 110 nL) caused current failure and
332 were rapidly discarded. No differences on peak areas for the eluted FQs were found in
333 the range between 5 and 10 s, and 5 s of eluent injection (*ca.* 50 nL) was selected to
334 minimize the possibility of current breakdowns. To conclude the elution optimization, we
335 investigated the pushing step of the elution plug from 15 to 90 s at 100 mbar. Non-
336 significant differences were found in the peak areas while current was stable in all cases,
337 hence 60 s was selected to ensure that the eluent plug already passed through the
338 microcartridge before applying the separation voltage.

339 Under these elution conditions, the composition of sample loading was investigated
340 introducing 20 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ standard mixtures in BGE (50 mM phosphate buffer at pH 7) or
341 water (Figure S5). Peak areas were much larger with BGE, which was selected as loading
342 composition. The influence of sample volume was investigated loading a 1 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$
343 standard mixture at 930 mbar from 5 to 30 min (Figure S6A). The results showed that
344 sorbent saturation and analyte breakthrough was not observed under the tested conditions,
345 which suggested the suitability of the HKUST-1@polymer as a high extraction efficiency
346 and large sample capacity sorbent for microscale applications. Saturation was neither
347 observed when the standard mixture was loaded at 2 bar (see Figure S6B), but a

348 significant reduction of microcartridge lifetime happened probably due to excessive
349 sorbent packing. For further experiments, unless otherwise stated, 10 min at 930 mbar
350 was set as sample loading conditions, as a good compromise between total analysis time,
351 sensitivity enhancement and microcartridge durability.

352 Finally, the concentration of the BGE was also investigated at 25 mM and 75 mM
353 phosphate (see Figure 2B). The 75 mM concentration was rapidly discarded because
354 current values were excessive, the Ohm's law was not fulfilled and current failure was
355 frequent. The best results in terms of peak area, repeatability and separation were
356 achieved with the 50 mM concentration, since at 25 mM concentration DAN was not
357 separated from the eluent components, which were migrating with the electroosmotic
358 flow (EOF). Using the 50 mM phosphate (pH 7) BGE, several volumes were tested for
359 washing after the loading step. At 930 mbar, duration times ranging from 30 to 90 s (*ca.*
360 3-9 μL) were tested (data not shown) and 60 s were enough to eliminate non-retained
361 molecules and to fill the capillary before applying the separation voltage. Figures 3B and
362 3C show the SPE-CE electropherograms for 0.1 and 1 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ standard mixtures under the
363 optimized conditions, respectively. As can be observed, an excellent sensitivity
364 enhancement was obtained compared to the analysis of a 1000 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ standard mixture
365 by CE (Figure 3C), without significant differences on peak efficiency or separation
366 resolution. The excellent method performance would be mainly due to the specific
367 structural and physicochemical features of the sorbent, but certain stacking effect during
368 the elution could not be discarded to explain the high preconcentration factors [24].

369 In order to investigate the retention mechanism of the FQs in the HKUST-1@polymer
370 under the optimized conditions, complementary Z-potential measurements were
371 performed. As it can be seen in Figure S7, under the loading conditions at pH 7, the
372 composite surface charge was negative (negative Z-potential value), while it was positive

373 under the acidic elution conditions (positive Z-potential value). This suggested that at pH
374 7, when the zwitterionic FQs presented zero net charge (see pK_a values in Table S1),
375 electrostatic interactions between the negatively charged composite and the cationic
376 moieties of FQs would be governing retention. Besides, π -interactions between the
377 benzene rings within the composite and FQs would be also important. In contrast, at
378 acidic pH when composite and FQs were positively charged, electrostatic repulsion
379 favored FQ elution.

380 In order to evaluate non-specific retention, $20 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ standard mixtures were also
381 analyzed by SPE-CE with microcartridges packed with the bare polymeric particles.
382 Enhancements in the sensitivity of 80, 75 and 55% in terms of peak area were observed
383 for DAN, EFX and DFX, respectively, with the HKUST-1@polymer compared to the
384 bare monolith. Thus, these results demonstrated the key role of the nano-MOF in the
385 efficient and selective extraction of FQs.

386 The optimized SPE-CE method was validated estimating the most relevant figures of
387 merit. The method was linear between 0.1 and $80 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ ($R^2 > 0.992$ for the three FQs),
388 and LOD and LOQ were 0.03 and $0.1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, respectively. The LOD could be further
389 decreased until 1 ng L^{-1} loading the sample for 30 min at 930 mbar (*ca.* $180 \mu\text{L}$, or this
390 volume at 2 bar for a shorter loading time) instead of for 10 min at 930 mbar (*ca.* $60 \mu\text{L}$).
391 These LOD values were 16,700 and 500,000 times lower than by CE-UV (0.5 mg L^{-1}),
392 and they were low enough to detect FQs at trace levels. Intra-day repeatability with a
393 single microcartridge was good: 4.0, 4.8 and 6.3% (% RSD of peak areas) for DAN, EFX
394 and DFX, respectively. As expected, inter-day reproducibility with different
395 microcartridges was slightly lower but acceptable: 6.7, 11.7 and 14.8% (% RSD of peak
396 areas) for DAN, EFX and DFX, respectively. Finally, a microcartridge could be reused

397 for 10 injections at $1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ without a significant decrease on the extraction recoveries
398 ($R>80\%$), separation and current performance.

399

400 **3.4. Application to real samples**

401 For the analysis of FQs in real samples, several complex matrices were tested to confirm
402 the wide applicability of the developed method. In order to avoid the microcartridge
403 saturation, simple and fast sample pretreatments were necessary. Only adjustment to 50
404 mM phosphate pH 7, centrifugation and filtration were applied to river water, and an
405 additional 1:10 dilution to human urine. Whole cow milk samples were deproteinized by
406 acetonitrile precipitation, and the dried supernatants were treated in a similar way. Figures
407 4 A-C i) show the SPE-CE electropherograms for the blank samples. Since the FQs could
408 not be detected in the blank samples, the samples were spiked at $1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ with the standard
409 mixture. Figures 4 A-C ii) illustrate the SPE-CE electropherograms of the spiked samples.
410 As can be observed, the three FQs could be clearly detected after preconcentration
411 without the interference of the rest of components from the sample matrix. Recoveries
412 for the three FQs in the different samples under the optimized SPE-CE conditions are
413 depicted in Table 1, and they ranged from 92 to 119% ($s<20\%$, $n=3$). These values
414 suggested the validity of the proposed method to monitor drugs at trace levels in several
415 complex matrices.

416

417 **3.5. Comparison with other on-line automated methods**

418 Finally, the developed HKUST-1@polymer-SPE-CE-UV method was compared with
419 other relevant on-line automated approaches described in the literature [39–48] (see Table
420 2). At first glance, the use of sophisticated and expensive MS and MS/MS detection is a
421 common practice in the analysis of FQs at trace level. However, the LOD by the

422 developed method, which uses conventional and accessible UV detection, was much
423 better or comparable to those achieved with expensive MS equipment [41,45–48]. Indeed,
424 the obtained LOD was similar to the values reported with fluorescence detection [40,44],
425 which is widely recognized for the trace detection of FQs. This sensitivity, jointly with
426 the facts that the fritless SPE-CE microcartridges are easily assembled with a few
427 micrograms of sorbent and the system does not require valves for operation (see Table
428 2), underlines the convenience of using the developed method. Pang and co-workers
429 developed an on-line SPE-HPLC method with fluorescence detection using as sorbent a
430 layer-by-layer MOF@polymer [44]. In this case, several valves, pumps and fluorescence
431 detection were required. Furthermore, 15 synthesis cycles were necessary to prepare the
432 MOF to obtain comparable LOD values to our study, which required only 4 cycles.
433 Regarding the method precision, the RSD values were similar in all cases except for those
434 obtained with certain approaches, which were slightly higher [45,46]. Another convenient
435 feature of the developed method was the small sample volume required. Excepting for
436 those methods based on SPE-CE [46–48], sample volumes larger than 1 mL were needed,
437 which would suppose a drawback with samples of limited availability (e.g. biological
438 fluids). To conclude the comparison, the recovery values were in general ranging between
439 70 and 125% excepting for a few studies affected by matrix effects [41,46]. Globally, the
440 developed HKUST-1@monolith-SPE-CE-UV method can be regarded as an attractive
441 and highly recommendable alternative for determination of FQs in complex samples.

442 **4. Conclusions**

443 An HKUST-1 nano-MOF was built layer-by-layer onto the surface of an organic polymer
444 resulting in a hybrid composite that was carefully characterized and used for the first time
445 as sorbent for SPE-CE-UV. The suitability of the HKUST-1@polymer as a highly
446 efficient and versatile sorbent for microextraction has been demonstrated by analyzing

447 FQs at trace levels in river water, human urine and whole cow milk samples. The large
448 active surface area and morphology of the hybrid composite allowed the rapid and simple
449 preparation of fritless particle-packed microcartridges and sensitivity enhancements up to
450 500,000 times compared to CE-UV, with minute sample loading ($\leq 180 \mu\text{L}$). The
451 performance of the method regarding linearity, repeatability, reproducibility, durability
452 and recoveries or matrix effect with real samples was also remarkable. Furthermore, it
453 could be easily adapted to analyze other ionizable and non-ionizable drugs or biomarkers
454 considering the mechanisms governing retention and elution from the hybrid composite.
455 Beyond SPE-CE, the achieved unprecedented sensitivity enhancement and appropriate
456 selectivity could expand the applicability of nano-MOF@polymer composites in other
457 microextraction techniques.

458

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470

471 **Author contributions:**

472 All authors contributed to conceptualization of this manuscript.

473 **-Héctor Martínez-Pérez-Cejuela:** methodology and design, formal analysis and
474 investigation, writing-original draft and revision

475 **-Fernando Benavente:** methodology and design, writing-review and editing,
476 supervision, funding acquisition

477 **-Ernesto F. Simó-Alfonso:** writing-review and editing, supervision, funding acquisition
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481

482 **Notes**

483 The authors declare no competing financial interest.

484

485 **References**

- 486 [1] H. Furukawa, K.E. Cordova, M. O’Keeffe, O.M. Yaghi, The chemistry and
487 applications of metal-organic frameworks, *Science* (80-.). 341 (2013) 1230444.
488 <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1230444>.
- 489 [2] M. Safaei, M.M. Foroughi, N. Ebrahimpour, S. Jahani, A. Omid, M. Khatami, A
490 review on metal-organic frameworks: Synthesis and applications, *TrAC - Trends*
491 *Anal. Chem.* 118 (2019) 401–425. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2019.06.007>.
- 492 [3] Z.Y. Gu, C.X. Yang, N. Chang, X.P. Yan, Metal-organic frameworks for analytical
493 chemistry: From sample collection to chromatographic separation, *Acc. Chem.*
494 *Res.* 45 (2012) 734–745. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ar2002599>.
- 495 [4] F.A. Hansen, S. Pedersen-Bjergaard, Emerging Extraction Strategies in Analytical
496 Chemistry, *Anal. Chem.* 92 (2020) 2–15.
497 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.9b04677>.
- 498 [5] M.Y. Masoomi, A. Morsali, P.C. Junk, Ultrasound assisted synthesis of a Zn(ii)
499 metal-organic framework with nano-plate morphology using non-linear
500 dicarboxylate and linear N-donor ligands, *RSC Adv.* 4 (2014) 47894–47898.
501 <https://doi.org/10.1039/c4ra09186h>.
- 502 [6] Y.V. Kaneti, J. Tang, R.R. Salunkhe, X. Jiang, A. Yu, K.C.W. Wu, Y. Yamauchi,
503 Nanoarchitected Design of Porous Materials and Nanocomposites from Metal-
504 Organic Frameworks, *Adv. Mater.* 29 (2017) 1604898.
505 <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201604898>.
- 506 [7] F. Bigdeli, F. Rouhani, A. Morsali, A. Ramazani, Ultrasonic-assisted synthesis of
507 the nanostructures of a Co(II) metal organic framework as a highly sensitive
508 fluorescence probe of phenol derivatives, *Ultrason. Sonochem.* 62 (2020) 104862.
509 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ultsonch.2019.104862>.

- 510 [8] A. Khoobi, M. Salavati-Niasari, M. Ghani, S.M. Ghoreishi, A. Gholami,
511 Multivariate optimization methods for in-situ growth of LDH/ZIF-8 nanocrystals
512 on anodized aluminium substrate as a nanosorbent for stir bar sorptive extraction
513 in biological and food samples, *Food Chem.* 288 (2019) 39–46.
514 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2019.02.118>.
- 515 [9] T. Wiwasuku, J. Othong, J. Boonmak, V. Ervithayasuporn, S. Youngme,
516 Sonochemical synthesis of microscale Zn(ii)-MOF with dual Lewis basic sites for
517 fluorescent turn-on detection of Al³⁺ and methanol with low detection limits, *Dalt.*
518 *Trans.* 49 (2020) 10240–10249. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d0dt01175d>.
- 519 [10] H. Martínez-Pérez-Cejuela, Ó. Mompó-Roselló, N. Crespi-Sánchez, C. Palomino
520 Cabello, M. Catalá-Icardo, E.F. Simó-Alfonso, J.M. Herrero-Martínez,
521 Determination of benzomercaptans in environmental complex samples by
522 combining zeolitic imidazolate framework-8-based solid-phase extraction and
523 high-performance liquid chromatography with UV detection, *J. Chromatogr. A.*
524 1631 (2020) 461580. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2020.461580>.
- 525 [11] S. Wang, Y. Lv, Y. Yao, H. Yu, G. Lu, Modulated synthesis of monodisperse
526 MOF-5 crystals with tunable sizes and shapes, *Inorg. Chem. Commun.* 93 (2018)
527 56–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inoche.2018.05.010>.
- 528 [12] H. Martínez-Pérez-Cejuela, M. Guíñez, E.F. Simó-Alfonso, P. Amorós, J. El
529 Haskouri, J.M. Herrero-Martínez, In situ growth of metal-organic framework
530 HKUST-1 in an organic polymer as sorbent for nitrated and oxygenated polycyclic
531 aromatic hydrocarbon in environmental water samples prior to quantitation by
532 HPLC-UV, *Microchim. Acta.* 187 (2020). [https://doi.org/10.1007/s00604-020-](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00604-020-04265-z)
533 [04265-z](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00604-020-04265-z).
- 534 [13] M. Shokrollahi, S. Seidi, L. Fotouhi, In situ electrosynthesis of a copper-based

535 metal–organic framework as nanosorbent for headspace solid-phase
536 microextraction of methamphetamine in urine with GC-FID analysis, *Microchim.*
537 *Acta.* 187 (2020) 548. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00604-020-04535-w>.

538 [14] R. Li, S. Li, Q. Zhang, Y. Li, H. Wang, Layer-by-layer assembled triphenylene-
539 based MOFs films for electrochromic electrode, *Inorg. Chem. Commun.* (2020)
540 108354. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inoche.2020.108354>.

541 [15] J. Zhao, B. Gong, W.T. Nunn, P.C. Lemaire, E.C. Stevens, F.I. Sidi, P.S. Williams,
542 C.J. Oldham, H.J. Walls, S.D. Shepherd, M.A. Browe, G.W. Peterson, M.D.
543 Losego, G.N. Parsons, Conformal and highly adsorptive metal–organic framework
544 thin films via layer-by-layer growth on ALD-coated fiber mats, *J. Mater. Chem.*
545 *A.* 3 (2015) 1458–1464. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c4ta05501b>.

546 [16] Y. Lv, X. Tan, F. Svec, Preparation and applications of monolithic structures
547 containing metal–organic frameworks, *J. Sep. Sci.* 40 (2017) 272–287.
548 <https://doi.org/10.1002/jssc.201600423>.

549 [17] N. Stock, S. Biswas, Synthesis of metal-organic frameworks (MOFs): Routes to
550 various MOF topologies, morphologies, and composites, *Chem. Rev.* 112 (2012)
551 933–969. <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr200304e>.

552 [18] Wahiduzzaman, K. Allmond, J. Stone, S. Harp, K. Mujibur, Synthesis and
553 Electrospaying of Nanoscale MOF (Metal Organic Framework) for High-
554 Performance CO₂ Adsorption Membrane, *Nanoscale Res. Lett.* 12 (2017) 1–12.
555 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s11671-016-1798-6>.

556 [19] X. Zhong, Y. Zhang, L. Tan, T. Zheng, Y. Hou, X. Hong, G. Du, X. Chen, Y.
557 Zhang, X. Sun, An aluminum adjuvant-integrated nano-MOF as antigen delivery
558 system to induce strong humoral and cellular immune responses, *J. Control.*
559 *Release.* 300 (2019) 81–92. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2019.02.035>.

- 560 [20] S. Homayoonnia, S. Zeinali, Design and fabrication of capacitive nanosensor based
561 on MOF nanoparticles as sensing layer for VOCs detection, *Sensors Actuators, B*
562 *Chem.* 237 (2016) 776–786. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2016.06.152>.
- 563 [21] A. Herbst, A. Khutia, C. Janiak, Brønsted instead of lewis acidity in functionalized
564 MIL-101Cr MOFs for efficient heterogeneous (nano-MOF) catalysis in the
565 condensation reaction of aldehydes with alcohols, *Inorg. Chem.* 53 (2014) 7319–
566 7333. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ic5006456>.
- 567 [22] S.A. Kitte, T.H. Fereja, M.I. Halawa, B. Lou, H. Li, G. Xu, Recent advances in
568 nanomaterial-based capillary electrophoresis, *Electrophoresis.* 40 (2019) 2050–
569 2057. <https://doi.org/10.1002/elps.201800534>.
- 570 [23] R.L.C. Voeten, I.K. Ventouri, R. Haselberg, G.W. Somsen, Capillary
571 Electrophoresis: Trends and Recent Advances, *Anal. Chem.* 90 (2018) 1464–1481.
572 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.8b00015>.
- 573 [24] M.C. Breadmore, W. Grochocki, U. Kalsoom, M.N. Alves, S.C. Phung, M.T.
574 Rokh, J.M. Cabot, A. Ghiasvand, F. Li, A.I. Shallan, A.S.A. Keyon, A.A.
575 Alhusban, H.H. See, A. Wuethrich, M. Dawod, J.P. Quirino, Recent advances in
576 enhancing the sensitivity of electrophoresis and electrochromatography in
577 capillaries and microchips (2016–2018), *Electrophoresis.* 40 (2019) 17–39.
578 <https://doi.org/10.1002/elps.201800384>.
- 579 [25] L. Pont, R. Pero-Gascon, E. Gimenez, V. Sanz-Nebot, F. Benavente, A critical
580 retrospective and prospective review of designs and materials in in-line solid-phase
581 extraction capillary electrophoresis, *Anal. Chim. Acta.* 1079 (2019) 1–19.
582 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2019.05.022>.
- 583 [26] L. Pont, F. Benavente, J. Barbosa, V. Sanz-Nebot, On-line immunoaffinity solid-
584 phase extraction capillary electrophoresis mass spectrometry using Fab´antibody

- 585 fragments for the analysis of serum transthyretin, *Talanta*. 170 (2017) 224–232.
586 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2017.03.104>.
- 587 [27] R. Pero-Gascon, V. Sanz-Nebot, M. V. Berezovski, F. Benavente, Analysis of
588 Circulating microRNAs and Their Post-Transcriptional Modifications in Cancer
589 Serum by On-Line Solid-Phase Extraction-Capillary Electrophoresis-Mass
590 Spectrometry, *Anal. Chem.* 90 (2018) 6618–6625.
591 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.8b00405>.
- 592 [28] R. Pero-Gascon, F. Benavente, Z. Minic, M. V. Berezovski, V. Sanz-Nebot, On-
593 line Aptamer Affinity Solid-Phase Extraction Capillary Electrophoresis-Mass
594 Spectrometry for the Analysis of Blood α -Synuclein, *Anal. Chem.* 92 (2020) 1525–
595 1533. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.9b04802>.
- 596 [29] L. Pont, G. Marin, M. Vergara-Barberán, L.G. Gagliardi, V. Sanz-Nebot, J.M.
597 Herrero-Martínez, F. Benavente, Polymeric monolithic microcartridges with gold
598 nanoparticles for the analysis of protein biomarkers by on-line solid-phase
599 extraction capillary electrophoresis-mass spectrometry, *J. Chromatogr. A*. 1622
600 (2020) 461097. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2020.461097>.
- 601 [30] H.H. Lauer, Rozing G.P., High performance capillary electrophoresis, 2nd Ed.,
602 Pags. 60-61, Waldbronn, Germany, 2014.
- 603 [31] T. Hong, W. Liu, M. Li, C. Chen, Click chemistry at the microscale, *Analyst*. 144
604 (2019) 1492–1512. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c8an01497c>.
- 605 [32] Y. Xu, Q. Cao, F. Svec, J.M.J. Fréchet, Porous polymer monolithic column with
606 surface-bound gold nanoparticles for the capture and separation of cysteine-
607 containing peptides, *Anal. Chem.* 82 (2010) 3352–3358.
608 <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac1002646>.
- 609 [33] F. Maya, C. Palomino Cabello, J.M. Estela, V. Cerdà, G. Turnes Palomino,

610 Automatic In-Syringe Dispersive Microsolid Phase Extraction Using Magnetic
611 Metal-Organic Frameworks, *Anal. Chem.* 87 (2015) 7545–7549.
612 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.5b01993>.

613 [34] S. Yang, F. Ye, Q. Lv, C. Zhang, S. Shen, S. Zhao, Incorporation of metal-organic
614 framework HKUST-1 into porous polymer monolithic capillary columns to
615 enhance the chromatographic separation of small molecules, *J. Chromatogr. A.*
616 1360 (2014) 143–149. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2014.07.067>.

617 [35] M. Giesbers, E.J. Carrasco-Correa, E.F. Simó-Alfonso, J.M. Herrero-Martínez,
618 Hybrid monoliths with metal-organic frameworks in spin columns for extraction
619 of non-steroidal drugs prior to their quantitation by reversed-phase HPLC,
620 *Microchim. Acta.* 186 (2019) 759 (1–9). [https://doi.org/10.1007/s00604-019-](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00604-019-3923-6)
621 [3923-6](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00604-019-3923-6).

622 [36] M.H. Yap, K.L. Fow, G.Z. Chen, Synthesis and applications of MOF-derived
623 porous nanostructures, *Green Energy Environ.* 2 (2017) 218–245.
624 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gee.2017.05.003>.

625 [37] A. Yang, P. Li, J. Zhong, Facile preparation of low-cost HKUST-1 with lattice
626 vacancies and high-efficiency adsorption for uranium, *RSC Adv.* 9 (2019) 10320–
627 10325. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c9ra01427f>.

628 [38] H. Martínez Pérez-Cejuela, E.J. Carrasco-Correa, A. Shahat, E.F. Simó-Alfonso,
629 J.M. Herrero-Martínez, Incorporation of metal-organic framework amino-
630 modified MIL-101 into glycidyl methacrylate monoliths for nano LC separation,
631 *J. Sep. Sci.* 42 (2019) 834–842. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jssc.201801135>.

632 [39] A. Prieto, S. Schrader, C. Bauer, M. Möder, Synthesis of a molecularly imprinted
633 polymer and its application for microextraction by packed sorbent for the
634 determination of fluoroquinolone related compounds in water, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*

- 635 685 (2011) 146–152. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2010.11.038>.
- 636 [40] E. Rodríguez, F. Navarro-Villoslada, E. Benito-Peña, M.D. Marazuela, M.C.
637 Moreno-Bondi, Multiresidue determination of ultratrace levels of fluoroquinolone
638 antimicrobials in drinking and aquaculture water samples by automated online
639 molecularly imprinted solid phase extraction and liquid chromatography, *Anal.*
640 *Chem.* 83 (2011) 2046–2055. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac102839n>.
- 641 [41] L. Kantiani, M. Farré, D. Barceló, Rapid residue analysis of fluoroquinolones in
642 raw bovine milk by online solid phase extraction followed by liquid
643 chromatography coupled to tandem mass spectrometry, *J. Chromatogr. A.* 1218
644 (2011) 9019–9027. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2011.09.079>.
- 645 [42] A. Manbohi, S.H. Ahmadi, In-tube magnetic solid phase microextraction of some
646 fluoroquinolones based on the use of sodium dodecyl sulfate coated Fe₃O₄
647 nanoparticles packed tube, *Anal. Chim. Acta.* 885 (2015) 114–121.
648 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2015.05.030>.
- 649 [43] C. Vakh, M. Alaboud, S. Lebedinets, D. Korolev, V. Postnov, L. Moskvina, O.
650 Osmolovskaya, A. Bulatov, An automated magnetic dispersive micro-solid phase
651 extraction in a fluidized reactor for the determination of fluoroquinolones in baby
652 food samples, *Anal. Chim. Acta.* 1001 (2018) 59–69.
653 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2017.11.065>.
- 654 [44] J. Pang, Y. Liao, X. Huang, Z. Ye, D. Yuan, Metal-organic framework-monolith
655 composite-based in-tube solid phase microextraction on-line coupled to high-
656 performance liquid chromatography-fluorescence detection for the highly sensitive
657 monitoring of fluoroquinolones in water and food samples, *Talanta.* 199 (2019)
658 499–506. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2019.03.019>.
- 659 [45] M. Tang, Y. Zhao, J. Chen, D. Xu, On-line multi-residue analysis of

660 fluoroquinolones and amantadine based on integrated microfluidic chip coupled to
661 triple quadrupole mass spectrometry, *Anal. Methods.* (2020).
662 <https://doi.org/10.1039/d0ay01641a>.

663 [46] F.J. Lara, A.M. García-Campaña, F. Alés-Barrero, J.M. Bosque-Sendra, In-line
664 solid-phase extraction preconcentration in capillary electrophoresis-tandem mass
665 spectrometry for the multiresidue detection of quinolones in meat by pressurized
666 liquid extraction, *Electrophoresis.* 29 (2008) 2117–2125.
667 <https://doi.org/10.1002/elps.200700666>.

668 [47] G. Morales-Cid, S. Cárdenas, B.M. Simonet, M. Valcárcel, Fully automatic sample
669 treatment by integration of microextraction by packed sorbents into commercial
670 capillary electrophoresis-mass spectrometry equipment: Application to the
671 determination of fluoroquinolones in urine, *Anal. Chem.* 81 (2009) 3188–3193.
672 <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac900234j>.

673 [48] D. Moreno-González, F.J. Lara, L. Gámiz-Gracia, A.M. García-Campaña,
674 Molecularly imprinted polymer as in-line concentrator in capillary electrophoresis
675 coupled with mass spectrometry for the determination of quinolones in bovine milk
676 samples, *J. Chromatogr. A.* 1360 (2014) 1–8.
677 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2014.07.049>.

678

679 **Figure captions**

680

681 **Figure 1.** Characterization studies of HKUST-1@polymer. A) Powder XRD pattern
682 profiles of the bare polymer, the hybrid composite and the simulated HKUST-1 MOF; B)
683 FT-IR spectra ($4000\text{-}500\text{cm}^{-1}$) of the hybrid composite, the bare polymer and the
684 HKUST-1 MOF; C) HRTEM and D) SEM micrographs of the hybrid composite.

685

686 **Figure 2.** SPE-CE-UV method optimization with a $20\ \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ standard mixture of FQs.
687 A) Effect of the eluent composition on the peak areas of the FQs (MeOH:H₂O:FA, v/v/v)
688 and B) electropherograms (280 nm) with different concentration of phosphate BGE at pH
689 7. Peak identification: 1) DAN, 2) EFX and 3) DFX. The rest of experimental conditions
690 (optimized method) are given in the experimental section.

691

692 **Figure 3.** Electropherograms (280 nm) for standard mixtures of FQs at different
693 concentrations by CE-UV (A) and SPE-CE-UV (B and C). Peak identification: 1) DAN;
694 2) EFX; 3) DFX. The rest of experimental conditions (optimized method) are given in the
695 experimental section.

696

697 **Figure 4.** SPE-CE-UV electropherograms (280 nm) for A) river water, B) human urine
698 and C) whole cow milk (i) blank samples and (ii) spiked samples with FQs at $1\ \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$.
699 Peak identification: 1) DAN; 2) EFX; 3) DFX. The experimental conditions (optimized
700 method) are given in the experimental section.